

Analysis on the reporting of suicide cases on selected online news websites

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Abstract

This study determined the rate of compliance of online news organizations according to the 2008 World Health Organization's Guidelines on Suicide Reporting, as reflected in the news articles pertaining to recent suicide cases in the Philippines. A combined method of qualitative approach for evaluating the compliance and violation of articles, and quantitative approach in measuring the rate of compliance of each media organization, this paper involved five suicidal cases reported in fifteen articles from twelve online news organizations. Percentage and mean were used in the treatment of data. Results discuss the rate of compliance and violation of each news article representing their respective online news organizations based on the nine (9) guidelines from WHO. Five suicide cases involving two provincial cases, two teenage suicides, and a celebrity death were reported by fifteen online news articles (three each suicide case) from twelve news organizations, one of which have three entries for all cases under study. This study also determined the most adhered guideline and the most violated guideline, as well as the news organization with the highest compliance rate and the highest violation rate. Findings also reveal that most news organizations did not follow or comply with the 2008 World Health Organization Guidelines on Reporting Suicide Cases, and there are guidelines that are most adhered or violated by online news organizations when reporting suicide cases in the Philippines.

Keywords: Suicide, compliance rate, violation, media reporting.

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Introduction

Filipinos are known to be happy people. Despite the series of adversities and calamities they endure, they are still able to find ways to smile. Optimism, or maintaining a positive mindset and looking at the brighter perspective in life, has been one of the key characteristics of Filipinos that is being looked up to, aside from their best-known trait of warm hospitality, strong faith, and resiliency. All these claims support the general notion that Filipinos love happiness, and they choose to be happy no matter how tough and challenging things can get – which the popular “*It's More Fun in the Philippines*” tagline banners to the world.

However, the latest results of the 2021 World Happiness Report reveal that the Filipinos were less happy in the previous year than the Philippines, and the Filipinos in particular, dropped at the 61st spot in the rankings, from the previous 52nd. The survey which was conducted by the United Nations Sustainable Development Solutions Network (UNSDSN) from the data of Gallup World Poll and Lloyd's Register Foundation has shown significant effects of the pandemic in the way Filipinos view life and happiness; and that they are at higher risk of developing serious mental health problems – which can lead to suicide.

The Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) recorded a significant 57% increase in the country's suicide rate in 2020 compared to the previous years. Suicide (labeled as *Intentional self-harm*) tolled 4,420 records of death last year thereby ranked as the 25th leading cause of death in the Philippines. There was also an average of 700 calls per day tallied by the National Center for Mental Health (NCMH) during March to August 2020, from the previous 400 monthly calls in 2019; most of which are anxiety-related concerns from the obvious effects of the pandemic – loss of work and financial instability, among others.

Along with the rising number of tallied suicide cases in the Philippines is the relevance of media and journalism in bringing these stories into the mainstream, therefore, reaching a wider and diverse array of audiences. Sinyor et al. (2018) mentioned that reporting on suicide cases creates a meaningful impact on suicide deaths and that journalists and media outlets, and organizations should carefully consider the specific content of reports before publication. It has become one of the most important roles of media and journalism, now more than ever, to not only report cases of suicide in the Philippines as raw stories but also to be more responsible and sensitive on how they deliver and present each story, becoming fully aware of its impact on the viewing/reading public. Luczon and Jerusalem (2021) cited the condemnation of the Cagayan de Oro Press Club (COPC) in the dissemination of personal information about sensitive and extremely stigmatized issues such as mental health, particularly suicide, as well as those that invade the privacy of the affected relatives and other individuals. They also recommended the World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines for media professionals in covering mental health and suicide, as young individuals and persons with diagnosed mental health problems are deemed vulnerable in this reference.

With media and journalism staging, the researcher, as an enthusiast in the communication field, aimed to understand the context of suicide reporting in the Philippines and how media, specifically online media organizations, adhere to the prescribed guidelines in reporting sensitive topics such as suicide cases.

Media and Suicide

Philips (1974) paved the early journey towards understanding the role of media in suicide cases, coining the phenomena called “Werther Effect” – a special risk associated to media which describes the apparition of copycat suicides after media reports on these cases are released; a media-induced imitation effects of suicidal behavior in audiences. The term was named after the novel written by Goethe (1774) entitled “The Sorrows of Young Werther” which have significantly caused a striking increase in the number of suicide cases following its publication. Since then, several case studies and research were conducted to further understand how media influences suicidal tendencies through its forms, including news reports.

Ha and Yang (2021) concluded the Werther effect as impactful on celebrity suicides in Korea, a country with higher suicide rates among other states. Their study reveals that a number of public suicides soar after media reports celebrity suicides, gaining an average of 16.4% increase after the day of the report; with females and younger subgroups who are more likely affected. It also stated that the public reacts more intensely to suicide incidents of personalities of the same gender as them and even imitates the suicidal methods of the celebrity. Results include recommendations on policymakers of their nation to implement regulations not only for traditional media but also for new media where the younger generation can have free access to unfiltered information.

The same was concluded in a systematic review and meta-analysis conducted by Niederkröthaler et al. (2010), stating that reports on celebrity deaths due to suicide have made meaningful impact on the total suicides. An increase of 13% spiked after the media reported a celebrity suicide case. After the method of suicide was reported, 30% increase in suicide deaths followed the same method. Although general reporting of celebrity suicide per se cannot be associated with the recent cases, some reports showing a more detailed and specific type of reporting are more likely to be associated in the rising number of suicide cases. His study also recommended interventions specifically guidelines for responsible media reporting which shall be widely implemented and promoted, especially on reports including deaths of celebrities and personalities.

Objectives of the Study

This study generally aims to determine the rate of compliance of online news organizations in reporting suicide cases in the Philippines. Specifically, the following objectives were sought to be met at the course of this research:

1. Select online news articles and reports on suicide cases from 2019.
2. Analyze different online media reports on suicide cases from 2019 based on WHO's Preventing Suicide: A Resource for Media Professionals.
3. Determine the rate of compliance of each media organization in every news article.

Research Methodology

This research follows a combined method of qualitative and quantitative approaches. McLeod (2019) defines a qualitative approach as the process of collecting, analyzing, and interpreting non-numerical data such as language and maybe in the form of text, video, photographs, or recordings; while the quantitative approach stirs information that can be quantified and can be reduced into numeric measurements. In this study, the qualitative method took place in the process of analysis on news articles and the guideline to which they comply or not; while the quantitative method is subscribed in determining the rate of compliance of news articles as well as their violation on the guidelines prescribed by the World Health Organization (WHO).

Participants

This study involved selected news articles and online news organizations as its participants or samples of the study. Random sampling is applied in the selection of news articles. The researcher selected five (5) suicide cases (two provincial cases, two teenage suicide cases, and one celebrity suicide) reported by online news organizations. The researcher looked at the credibility and legitimacy of the online news organizations producing the articles to ensure the quality of news articles to be studied. In totality, there were fifteen (15) news articles from twelve (12) online news organizations which were subjects of the research.

Research Instruments

In order to supply necessary data for the conduct of the study, the researcher explored the web searching for articles needed in the study. Once done, the researcher referred to the guideline entitled “Preventing Suicide, A Resource for Media Professionals,” a reference guide released by World Health Organization in 2008. This publication outlines the “evidence on the impact of media reporting of suicide, and, using this evidence, provides a resource for media professionals about how to report suicide. Guidelines pertaining to reporting suicide cases are as follows:

1. Take the opportunity to educate the public about suicide.
2. Avoid language which sensationalizes or normalizes suicide or presents it as a solution to problems.
3. Avoid prominent placement and undue repetition of stories about suicide.
4. Avoid explicit description of the method used in a completed or attempted suicide.
5. Avoid providing detailed information about the site of a completed or attempted suicide.
6. Word headlines carefully.
7. Exercise caution in using photographs or video footage.
8. Take particular care in reporting celebrity suicides.
9. Show consideration for people bereaved by suicide.
10. Provide information about where to seek help.
11. Recognize that media professionals themselves may be affected by stories about suicide.

However, only nine (9) out of eleven (11) guidelines were referenced in the study because of its applicability in the analysis and evaluation. These guidelines were the core basis of the researcher in determining the rate of compliance and violations of selected news organizations in reporting suicide cases.

Research Procedures

After news stories from different online news organizations were thoroughly selected, the researcher analyzed each subject based on WHO’s 2008 guidelines on suicide reporting with the exception of Item 3 and 11 due to lack of applicability in the samples. The researcher also applied interpretations in the course of data analysis to efficiently represent the compliance and violations of each online news organization in the reference guidelines. Interpretations were:

V – Violated; N – Not Violated/Complied; NA – Not Applicable

The researcher used a tabular format in the presentation of data. Once each article is analyzed and evaluated based on its compliance to the nine guidelines released by WHO, the researcher computed for the percentage of compliance.

Results and Discussion

After thorough analysis and evaluation on the news organizations and their published articles related to suicide cases, the following results were obtained:

Selected Online News Organizations

After careful selection of news articles related to suicide cases, the researcher was able to evaluate fifteen (15) online news reports from twelve (12) media news organizations discussing five (5) suicide cases: two (2) local and provincial suicide reports covered by the media organizations; two (2) reports on student suicide case; and one (1) celebrity suicide case.

Analysis on Media News Reports

Table 1. Analysis on the compliance and violation rate of news organizations in each guideline

Guidelines	SHS Student Suicide			Cebuano Teen Suicide			Pangasinan Pastor Suicide			College Student Suicide			Broadcast Journalist Joseph Ubalde's Suicide		
	Inquirer	CNN Philippines	GMA News	Cebu Daily News	Rappler	Sun Star Cebu	Inquirer	Bombo Radyo	Abante Tonite	Inquirer	Manila Bulletin	Daily Tribune	Pilipino Star Ngayon	PEP	Abante Tonite
Take the opportunity to educate the public about suicide.	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	N	N	V
Avoid language which sensationalizes or normalizes suicide or presents it as a solution to problems.	N	N	N	V	N	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	N	N
Avoid explicit description of the method used in a completed or attempted suicide.	V	V	V	V	N	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	N	N	N
Avoid providing detailed information about the site of a completed or attempted suicide.	V	V	V	V	N	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	V
Word headlines carefully.	V	V	V	V	N	N	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	N	N
Exercise caution in using photographs or video footage.	N	N	V	N	N	N	N	N	V	V	N	N	N	N	N
Take particular care in reporting celebrity suicides.	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	V	N	N
Show due consideration for people bereaved by suicide.	N	N	N	N	N	N	V	V	V	N	V	V	N	N	N
Provide information about where to seek help.	N	N	V	N	N	N	N	V	N	N	V	V	V	V	V

Presented in the table are the detailed evaluation of the researcher in each news article from media organizations and their compliance in the guidelines presented from WHO’s 2008 Suicide Reporting Reference.

Among the nine (9) guidelines, Guideline 4 which is “*Avoid providing detailed information about the site of a completed or attempted suicide*” with fourteen (14) violations and only one (1) compliance garnered only 7% compliance rate from all articles, was determined as the Most Violated Guideline, following the observation that most news reports mentioned specific details which they perceived to be relevant in the report. It was followed by Guideline 1 “*Take the opportunity to educate the public about suicide*” with thirteen (13) violations and two (2) compliances tallying 13% compliance rate. Guideline 3 “*Avoid explicit description of the method used in a completed or attempted suicide*” garnered eleven (11) violations and four (4) compliances with 27% compliance rate; while Guideline 5 “*Word headlines carefully*” also tallied the same 27% compliance rate.

Guideline 6 “*Exercise caution in using photographs or video footages*” with only three (3) violations and twelve (12) compliances garnering 80% compliance rate topped as the Most Adhered Guideline, as most news organizations observed ethical presentation of sensitive photographs and images in their reports (using black and white filter, blurred images, etc.). Guideline 8 “*Show due consideration for people bereaved by the suicide*” followed with five (5) violations and seven (10) compliances tallying 67% compliance rate. Guideline 9 “*Provide information about where to seek help*” garnered eight (8) violations and seven (7) compliances comprising 47% compliance rate.

Guideline 7 “*Take particular care in reporting celebrity suicides*”, particularly applicable only to the celebrity case, which was reported by three online news organizations, garnered two (2) compliances and one (1) violation with 67% compliance rate.

Rate of Compliance of News Organizations

Indicated below is the table presenting the rate of compliance and violation of involved online news organizations in the study:

Table 2. Rate of compliance and violations of online news organizations

	SHS Student Suicide			Cebuano Teen Suicide			Pangasinan Pastor Suicide			College Student Suicide			Broadcast Journalist Joseph Ubalde’s Suicide			Mean
	Inquirer	CNN Philippines	GMA News	Cebu Daily News	Rappler	Sun Star Cebu	Inquirer	Bombo Radyo	Abante Tonite	Inquirer	Manila Bulletin	Daily Tribune	Pilipino Star Ngayon	PEP	Abante Tonite	
Compliance	50%	50%	25%	38%	88%	50%	75%	13%	13%	75%	13%	13%	44%	77%	67%	46%
Violation	50%	50%	75%	62%	12%	50%	25%	87%	87%	25%	87%	87%	56%	23%	33%	54%

As presented, twelve (12) online news organizations were particularly involved in the selected suicide cases recently reported from 2019, with Inquirer having three (3) entries – one article in the three suicide cases.

In terms of compliance, Rappler, in its report about the Cebuano Teen suicide, recorded the highest rate of compliance with 88% (7 compliance, 1 violation, 1 Not Applicable Guideline), followed by Philippine Entertainment Portal (PEP) in its report about the Celebrity Suicide with seven (7) compliances and two (2) violations comprising 77% compliance rate. Inquirer, in its

reports about one provincial suicide case and one teen suicide case, both garnered six (6) compliances and two (2) violations with one guideline not applicable to the case, tallying a 75% compliance rate for both articles.

Bombo Radyo in their report about one local suicide case, topped the news organizations with the most violated guidelines with an 87% violation rate (7 violations and 1 compliance), together with Manila Bulletin and Daily Tribune in their reports about teenage suicide, and Abante Tonight in its report on provincial suicide case with the same record and violation rate; making them the least-complying online news organizations.

Inquirer, the only online news organization with more than one article discussing suicide cases (two teen suicide cases and one provincial suicide case) tallied an overall eight (8) compliances and sixteen (16) violations with a combined compliance rate of 50% in all three articles.

Conclusions

Twelve online news organizations included in this study have an over-all compliance rate of 46% and a violation rate of 54%. Fifteen online news reports on suicide cases that were analyzed from twelve different news organizations show that they do not follow the World Health Organization's 2008 Guidelines on Suicide Reporting. The most violated guideline is the guidelines on disclosing the details of the suicide. The most adhered guideline is the caution exercised on using photos and videos of the suicide site and the person who died on suicide.

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